

EFKLIDES' METACOGNITIVE MODEL (2008); BENEFITS FOR THE CONTINUOUS TRAINING OF TEACHING STAFF

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Abstract:

Metacognition - an indisputable conceptual core whereby individuals are aware of the knowledge they have about their own information processing abilities, as well as knowledge about the nature of cognitive tasks and the strategies used to cope with tasks, as well as the efforts made to self-monitor and control their own thoughts and actions.

In the specialized literature there are multiple models and theories, more or less different, which tried to highlight the complexity of the formation and functioning of metacognition.

Efklides describes metacognition as a multidimensional construct that encompasses metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive experiences, and metacognitive regulation.

In the self-management of professional development and in educational practice, teachers with metacognitive skills, developed on the basis of the model proposed by Efklides, ensure that they successfully design/manage their own teaching career, can make professional development plans, can objectively monitor their behaviors, they can adjust the strategies, evaluate the achieved performances and automatically reflect the activities undertaken. Metacognitive experiences have the role of identifying and setting goals, motivating themselves, as well as developing the resilience and confidence to engage in and succeed in lifelong learning and promote their professional development.

Keywords: Metacognition, Teacher Education, Professional development

1. Introduction

Currently, the challenges of the teaching profession require the continuous training of teachers, understood as a process that involves the constant revision of their pedagogical practice, their teaching style, their professional competences, but which should stimulate a critical and reflective perspective, giving teachers the means of autonomous thinking

and to facilitate the dynamics of participatory self-education. Nóvoa (1992) considers that this type of continuing education involves a personal investment, a free and creative work on one's own paths and projects, in order to build an identity, which is also a professional identity. Continuous teacher training requires involvement, investment and active attitude, essential aspects for building autonomous thinking. Starting from these considerations, we appreciate that the development of teachers' metacognitive skills facilitates the active, rational-pragmatic involvement of teachers in the professional development process, and the affirmation of these skills in building and managing one's own path generates visible progress in professional performance, thus leading to a successful career.

With the appearance of the *Recommendation of the European Parliament and the Council on key competences from the perspective of lifelong learning* (2006/962/EC) which structures the "European training profile" based on eight key competences, metacognition, as an innovative dimension in structuring the curriculum, began to be intensively researched in direct relation to:

- critical thinking (Flavell, 1979; Kuhn, 1999; Hennessey, 1999; Martinez, 2006; Bensley & Spero, 2014), reflective thinking (Hofer, 2004);
- academic learning and collaborative learning (Stancescu, Draghicescu & Petrescu, 2018);
- performance monitoring and self-regulated learning (Schuster et al, 2020; Dignath, 2021; Taouki, Lallier & Soto, 2022);
- learning assessment (Wiliam, 2011; Baas et al., 2015).

Metacognition is used not only in fields of human knowledge, but also in professional fields, due to the fact that it involves awareness of one's own learning process through self-control, self-appreciation and self-improvement activities with the aim of transforming the conditions of knowledge and learning. Metacognition represents "the act of reflexive self-observation, understanding and regulation of one's own cognitive processes, of the way of building and using cognitive schemes, of learning and knowledge strategies" (Bocoş, 2013, p. 59); it is self-appraisal and management of one's own cognitive system (self-management), aspects that Paris & Winograd fit into what they call "self-efficacy theory" (Paris & Winograd, 1990, apud. Cerghit, 2002, p. 249).

Studies on the development of metacognition in teachers are focused on the component elements and metacognitive strategies and reveal the impact of metacognitive skills on successful classroom management, on the process of self-regulation of learning and improvement of real activity, the development of a sense of self-efficacy.

Metacognition is one of the key elements that facilitate individuals' ability to possess and effectively use effective professional development management strategies, identify weaknesses, and build new career development skills/capabilities.

Metacognition turns out to be a multidimensional structure containing different types of information and processes, leading to the possibility of developing models and theories, more or less different, which tried to highlight the complexity of the formation and functioning of this process (Bogar, 2018): *Flavell's model of cognitive monitoring* (1979), *Pressley's good information processing model*, *Borkowski and Schneider* (1989), *T.O. Nelson and L.Narens's metacognitive model* (1994), *Schraw and Moshman's metacognitive model* (1995), *Tobias and Everson's metacognitive model* (2002), *Efklides' metacognitive model* (2008).

2. Efklides' metacognitive model (2008)

One of the most comprehensive and analytical models, Efklides' metacognitive model consists of several stages and explains the concept of metacognition in detail. According to this model, metacognition is divided into three social levels, individual awareness and the two non-cognitive levels. This model also consists of three dimensions: 1. Metacognitive knowledge, 2. Metacognitive experiences, and 3. Metacognitive skills.

Fig.1. Efklides metacognitive model (according Efklides, 2008, p.283)

According to this model, metacognitive information contain information about the individual's tasks, goals, and strategies. Due to metacognitive experiences, individuals become aware of when and where they should use information. In other words, metacognitive experiences stand between the individual and the tasks. Metacognitive skills mean the individual selection of appropriate strategies during the learning process.

I. Metacognitive knowledge (MK) is knowledge stored in memory and it comprises models of cognitive processes such as language and memory. The metacognitive knowledge refers to what individuals know about their own knowledge or about knowledge in general and it includes information about what factors and variables act and interact to influence in a certain way the course and results of the knowledge approach. This metacognitive knowledge refers to the variables "person", "task" and "strategy" and it includes knowledge about oneself, from the position of a person who learns (learner), and the factors that could influence performance, knowledge about strategies and knowledge about the moment (when?) and the reason (why?) of using certain strategies (Borca, 2014, p. 310). We refer here to three types of metacognitive awareness: declarative, procedural and conditional knowledge (Brown, 1987; Jacobs & Paris, 1987).

II. Metacognitive skills (MS) – awareness of what the individual does concretely, which involves actions (Cerghit, 2008). Metacognitive skills are used to consciously guide, monitor, control and regulate cognitive and affective processes and states, in order to build the most effective own knowledge and learning activities. There are three categories of essential skills: planning (selecting appropriate strategies and allocating the necessary resources to accomplish the task), monitoring (awareness of the level of understanding and solving the task while performing it) and testing (putting it into practice), reviewing and appraising strategies (appraising the methods used, but also the objectives and results).

A number of studies indicate that both metacognitive knowledge and regulatory skills such as planning are related to the appraisal process (Baker, 1989). The concept of metacognitive regulation has thus been expanded to include replanning and critical appraisal of cognitive tasks

and goals (Brown, 1987; Cross & Paris, 1988; Paris & Winograd, 1990; Schraw et al. al., 2006; Dunlosky, Metcalfe, 2009; Whitebread et al., 2009).

Metaknowledge continuously interacts with components of metacognitive skills and is constantly self-regulating: declarative cognition facilitates the regulation of problem solving, judgments of task monitoring ability are significantly related to accuracy of observations and performance, and knowledge of strategies is related to self-reported strategy use.

III. An essential component of metacognition that has traditionally received less attention from researchers is **metacognitive experiences (MEs)** (Efklides, 2006). Metacognitive experiences refer to the conscious feelings during an activity that we have about the task to be solved and the processing of information related to it. However, they can appear both before and after the activity.

The metacognitive experiences represent the interface between the person and the task, the person's awareness of the characteristics of the task, the fluency of cognitive processing, the progress towards the set goal, the effort exerted on the cognitive processing and the result of the processing (Efklides, 2008, p. 279). They take the form of metacognitive feelings, metacognitive judgments/estimates, and task-specific online knowledge. Efklides (2001) considers that the feeling of knowledge, the feeling of familiarity, and the feeling of trust are some indicative metacognitive feelings extensively studied in metamemory research.

The teachers' metacognitive experiences include both cognitive and affective feelings when they go through different stages in their professional development (for example, a sense of achievement when they get their teaching degrees, when they have special results in different activities at the level of educational units or when they successfully finish the didactic tasks).

There is an interdependent relationship between the component elements of metacognition. Thus, the metacognitive skills depend on the metacognitive knowledge that the individual possesses and are influenced by metacognitive experiences. Through the cognitive regulation loop, the metacognitive skills use task-specific knowledge as well as metaknowledge and operate on knowledge by calling on specific strategies to analyse task demands and appraise. For metacognitive skills to be activated, there must be awareness of cognitive processing fluency, after which this information

is conveyed by metacognitive experiences, such as feelings of familiarity, difficulty, or confidence (Efklides, 2018).

Based on empirical research, it has been shown that this “knowing of knowing” is often reflected and operationalized as self-regulatory actions, such as creating and implementing a plan for approaching a learning task. Thus, metacognition remains a complex and somewhat “mysterious” construct, not to mention issues such as when it occurs and how it is measured (Efklides & Misailidi, 2010).

3. Benefits of metacognition in professional development

Metacognition is understood as knowing knowledge itself, or even learning how to learn. This concept “includes any knowledge or cognitive activity that aims at or adjusts any aspect of any cognitive enterprise” (Flavell, Miller and Miller, 1999, p. 125). In the professional development of teachers, metacognition proposes a reflection on the professional activity and the way in which professional competences are developed, including their awareness, control and transformation by engaging in different learning situations. An example of metacognitive activity is when, before developing the professional development project, we consciously analyse the steps to be taken and the material we have at our disposal and the strategies we can adopt. So, the procedure used to undertake the project is the cognitive activity itself.

Becoming self-aware, we develop the ability to analyse the requirements of the task to be performed and relate it to the reality that presents itself; we can reflect on information, determine the purpose of the activity to be performed, notice what is new and familiar and detect levels of difficulty, and finally decide where and when to start training activities.

By involving metacognition in the process of continuing teacher education, they are given the opportunity to think about how to learn and, consequently, how to teach, in order to redefine their pedagogical practice and their perception as researchers of this practice.

Bransford, Brown, & Cocking (2007) believe that continuing education makes it indispensable to engage teachers as active participants in their learning, focusing their attention on critical elements and allowing them to appraise their own progress towards understanding, only using processes specific to metacognition.

At the same time, important implications of metacognition are also for pedagogical practice, especially in terms of teaching teachers to teach students metacognitive strategies, but for this to be possible, they must develop their own metacognitive capacities that will later be integrated into practice.

In the process of continuous training of teaching staff, the metacognitive ability possessed by a teacher consists in reflecting on one's own professional activity and the lifelong learning process. The metacognitive competence that must be possessed by the teacher is not only the knowledge of metacognition, but also the metacognitive skills of the teacher in the design of learning, and based on the metacognitive experiences they will be able to solve the problems faced by teachers in the learning process. Metacognitive competence is the key for a teacher to reflect on his/her own work and support his/her own and others' learning process.

Also, referring to the implications in the teaching career, the metacognitive factors of managing resources and information, by integrating various learning experiences, lead to the development of strategies for the future and help them to appraise themselves as learners, as they are already engaged in metacognitive practices of identifying and situating them in learning contexts, planning, and monitoring their cognitive processes.

Metacognition allows the active processing of previous experience, to modify, reconstruct or use it to perform a new task, for the expansion of new knowledge, new understanding and interpretation. By explaining how people regulate their own thinking to improve their effectiveness in learning and work, metacognition has over time acquired central importance in successful learning.

For the teacher, the attitude of thinking about thinking itself, learning about learning itself, is the opportunity to expand the possibilities of self-understanding and understanding of others and the world. Cochran-Smith and Lytle (1993) believe that teachers use their knowledge to construct perspectives, choose actions, manage dilemmas, interpret and create programmes, make strategic choices, and define their own teaching responsibilities. Teachers must possess the skills necessary for "self-analytical thinking" because it "involves reflecting on one's teaching and practice, inquiring about it, exploring it and then taking action to improve or change it" (Duffy, Miller, et .al, 2009, p.78).

4. Conclusions

The development of metacognitive competence in teachers can mean the cultivation of the “seventh sense” which differentiates individuals in terms of their performance, along with other factors such as intelligence, memory, attention, but also motivation, anxiety, attitude towards the learning activity, without excluding the differences due to age, gender or the social context in which the learning takes place.

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Developing metacognition in teachers means building their capacities to learn to learn throughout life and promoting their professional development. This fact allows teachers to develop a meta-perspective on continuous training activities and to be actors in building their own “savoir faire”, the reflection strategy regarding the professionalization of the teaching career. Transferring the specific elements of self-regulated learning to professional self-development we can argue that teachers set goals for their professional development, in order to then monitor, regulate and control their activity, motivation and behaviour, guided and constrained by their goals and the contextual characteristics of the environment (Pintrich, 2000, p. 453). Consequently, self-regulation of learning is an active and constructive process in which the interaction of three essential components – cognition, motivation and metacognition – serves to govern learning, with influences on the self-management of continuing education (Schraw et al., 2006).

In the development of this competence there are a number of external factors that depend on the circumstances in which the competent action is carried out and refer to the task, situation and context. Teachers actively and continuously build the knowledge necessary for their professional life. The relationship between personal factors and social contribution is interdependent because neither social nor personal contributions are enough, the social experience being important for articulating and ensuring access to performance requirements at work (Billet, 2008, apud. Dumitriu, Timofti, Dumitriu, 2011).

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